
Hardware-Saturated Denoising: Accelerating LLaDA-MoE via Permuted Expert Dispatch

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Abstract

Diffusion-based language models (DLMs), such as LLaDA offer distinct advantages in parallel generation but often lag behind autoregressive models in complex logical reasoning. While our work initial work utilized SFT, DPO and GRPO on distilled Chain-of-Thought (CoT) data from DeepSeek-V3.2, the high inference latency (≈ 1.5 minutes for 300 tokens over 80 denoising steps) rendered GRPO-based reasoning improvements computationally prohibitive. To address this, we propose a novel method for distributing tokens across experts via memory optimization and parallel GPU memory access. This approach significantly accelerates generation speed using the original LLaDA framework, ultimately providing a viable pathway for future GRPO-scale reasoning enhancements.

1 Introduction

We focus on accelerating model generation by addressing the CPU-overhead bottleneck. We evaluate several optimization strategies, including custom Triton kernels and refined native PyTorch implementations. Profiling indicates that our generation process is primarily CPU-bound; on an NVIDIA A100 (80GB), Streaming Multiprocessor (SM) utilization peaks at only 30–40% during Group Relative Policy Optimization (GRPO) experiments and inference across various batch sizes. This stands in stark contrast to Supervised Fine-Tuning (SFT) and Direct Preference Optimization (DPO) training—where we denoise randomly masked tokens sampled from a Beta(2, 20) distribution—which achieves 90–100% SM utilization. Benchmark results for the LLaDA-8B-Dense custom generation function reveal that the Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) variant exhibits significantly higher latency than its dense counterpart. An analysis of the LLaDAMoESparseMoeBlock implementation within `modelling_llada` shows that sparse GPU memory accesses during token routing severely degrade GPU efficiency. To address these limitations, we propose `FastLLADAMoE`, a class designed to maximize GPU parallelism and minimize host-side overhead.

2 Related Work & Motivation

Diffusion-Based Language Models. The paradigm shift from sequential autoregressive generation to parallel denoising was catalyzed by the introduction of Large Language Diffusion with Masking (LLaDA) Nie et al. [2024]. By treating text generation as a multi-step remasking process, LLaDA-based architectures offer significant advantages in parallel token throughput and long-context consistency compared to traditional causal transformers. The recent scaling of these models into Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) frameworks, such as LLaDA-MoE Zhu et al. [2025], InclusionAI [2024], has enabled massive parameter expansion while maintaining manageable active-parameter counts Shazeer et al. [2017], Zhu et al. [2025]. However, the block-wise iterative refinement process in LLaDA introduces specific challenges: the model must perform multiple forward passes to

denoise a single block, making the system highly sensitive to any overhead in the expert routing and dispatch logic.

MoE Optimization: From CPU-Bound to Compute-Bound. Since the inception of sparsely-gated MoE Shazeer et al. [2017], the primary bottleneck in low-batch inference has shifted from raw FLOPS to host-side dispatch overhead and fragmented memory access DeepSeek-AI [2024]. Traditional implementations often suffer from sequential kernel launches for each expert, leading to severe under-utilization of Streaming Multiprocessors (SM) on high-end hardware. While native PyTorch weight stacking was an initial step toward parallelization, it failed to eliminate the synchronization penalties inherent in sparse routing DeepSeek-AI [2024]. Our work builds upon the strategy of custom weight stacking for experts and ensuring contiguous access to tokens in GPU memory. By implementing a *Sort-Compute-Scatter* pipeline, we explicitly target the elimination of host-device synchronization gaps, transitioning the MoE forward pass into a hardware-saturated, compute-bound state with significantly reduced CPU overhead.

3 Generating answer

In this paper, we propose an optimized answer generation framework via the FastLLADAMoE class. An analysis of the LLaDAMoESparseMoeBlock implementation within modelling_llada shows that sparse GPU memory accesses during token routing (e.g., via `torch.where`) severely degrade GPU efficiency. This causes significant memory fragmentation and induces a shift from a compute-bound to a memory-bound regime, limited by host-side (CPU) overhead. To circumvent these limitations, we propose a method utilizing weight stacking for the expert projections (`w_gate` and `w_up`). By implementing pre-routing and post-sorting mechanisms, we enable experts to process tokens as a contiguous stack. This approach facilitates parallel token access across experts and decreases host-device latency by reducing synchronization to a single CPU-GPU call—specifically to convert expert counts to a list—prior to the SwiGLU loop.

Figure 1: Structure of MoE in LLADA MoE, with way of generating answer [Zhu et al., 2025]

At Figure 1 we demonstrate internal simple structure of generating answer with experts from LLaDA MoE authors paper [Zhu et al., 2025].

4 Remake MoE

The proposed architecture for optimized GPU-based generation is illustrated in Figure 2. We first extract the router logit matrix from the gate layer and apply a softmax activation. We then perform *top-k* selection to assign experts to each token. Following this, the expert assignments are sorted, allowing us to map the original indices to contiguous token blocks in memory. Subsequently, we perform a binning operation to calculate the number of tokens assigned to each expert. The token matrix is then partitioned into a list of sub-matrices based on these counts, and an output buffer is initialized. During the forward pass, we iterate through the partitioned token groups. Within each loop iteration, the SwiGLU activation is computed on the relevant token subsets using the corresponding expert weights. We then apply the router weights to the SwiGLU output to produce weighted chunks, which are aggregated into the final output matrix. This approach yields a result mathematically identical to the native MoE implementation while significantly reducing latency by maintaining memory contiguity.

Figure 2: Scheme of Fast Forward MoE at LLADA

5 Benchmarks

We evaluated the performance of our implementation using three primary metrics: CUDA Latency (ms) (Figure 3b), Throughput (tokens/s) (Figure 3a), and Total Execution Time (s) (Figure 3c) relative to generated sequence length. To ensure statistical consistency, all experiments were conducted using the configurations listed in Table 1, with each measurement averaged over eight independent runs. CUDA latency was captured using `torch.cuda.Event` to measure the time differences within the generation process. Total execution time was measured using Python’s `time` module, supplemented by `torch.cuda.synchronize()` to ensure accurate device-side timing. Furthermore, we monitored hardware utilization metrics—specifically Streaming Multiprocessor (SM) utilization (%) and Memory Controller utilization (%)—using the `pynvml` library at each generation step (Figure 4). The observed low utilization of the SM and Memory Controller in the baseline is attributed to significant CPU overhead during single-batch inference, which prevents optimal GPU saturation.

Table 1: Hyperparameters used for generation experiments.

Parameter	Value
Denoising steps	15
Max length (L)	50, 100, ..., 450
Block length	$L/5$
Temperature	0.0
CFG scale	0.0
Remasking strategy	low_confidence
Batch size	1
GPU	A100 40GB \times 1
Transformers version	4.57.6

The generation pipeline was adapted from the official implementation InclusionAI [2024]. According to the results in Figure 4, the mean ratios for the evaluated hardware metrics (FastLLaDAMoE vs. baseline) are:

$$\text{Ratio}_{\text{SM Util}} = 1.2541 \pm 0.0009, \quad \text{Ratio}_{\text{Mem BW}} = 1.9251 \pm 0.0066 \quad (1)$$

For these metrics, we truncated the baseline data to the length of the FastLLaDAMoE sequences, as our optimized method demonstrates significantly higher generation speed. Corresponding to the results in Figure 3b, the mean CUDA time ratio is:

$$\text{Ratio}_{\text{CUDA time}} = 1.8883 \pm 0.0030 \quad (2)$$

Total execution time (Figure 3c) shows a similar performance improvement. Furthermore, a linear regression analysis of the throughput metrics in Figure 3a provides the following slopes and fit statistics:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Slopes:} \quad & k_{\text{baseline}} = 0.3074 \pm 6.0287 \times 10^{-4}, \quad k_{\text{optimized}} = 0.1608 \pm 4.4348 \times 10^{-4} \\ \text{Linearity:} \quad & R_{\text{baseline}}^2 = 0.9999, \quad R_{\text{optimized}}^2 = 0.9999 \\ \text{Significance:} \quad & p_{\text{baseline}} < 10^{-13}, \quad p_{\text{optimized}} < 10^{-13} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Finally, to ensure parity in generation quality, we evaluated both models on 50 samples from the GSM8K test set. Both implementations achieved 50% accuracy. Minor variance in specific responses is attributed to the stochastic nature of the generation process. While this accuracy is lower

than the state-of-the-art results (82.41% Zhu et al. [2025]) due to our specific inference constraints (max length 128, block length 32), these results empirically validate that FastLLaDAMoE provides substantial throughput gains without compromising model performance.

(a) Generated tokens per second

(b) CUDA Execution Time

(c) Total Time Elapsed

Figure 3: Performance metrics comparison: Throughput, Latency, and Total Time.

Hardware Utilization Comparison: With Patching vs. Without Patching

Figure 4: Hardware characteristics during generation

6 Experimental Results

Our evaluation of the FastLLaDAMoE architecture demonstrates a successful transition of diffusion-based MoE inference from a memory-bound, CPU-bottlenecked state to a compute-saturated regime. By eliminating the overhead associated with fragmented memory access and redundant host-device synchronization, we achieve significant gains across all primary performance vectors.

6.1 Execution Speed and Throughput

As illustrated in Figures 3b and 3c, the optimized implementation consistently achieves a **1.89× reduction in CUDA execution time** across the tested sequence length spectrum. Total wall-clock (total time elapsed) shows a congruent improvement, confirming that our reduction in host-device synchronization effectively mitigates Python-level dispatch latency. In terms of throughput (Figure 3a), the linear scaling characteristic of LLaDA generation is preserved ($R^2 = 0.9999$), but with a substantially higher baseline. This indicates that our optimization scales predictably with sequence length while providing a constant-time reduction in per-step denoising overhead.

6.2 Hardware Efficiency and SM Saturation

The most critical evidence of our optimization’s success is found in the hardware utilization metrics (Figure 4). By restructuring expert computation into contiguous memory blocks via the *Sort-Compute-Scatter* pipeline, we achieved:

- **1.25× Increase in SM Utilization:** This gain reflects higher occupancy and better instruction-level parallelism, as the GPU is no longer idling while waiting for the CPU to dispatch individual expert kernels.
- **1.93× Memory Bandwidth Utilization Improvement:** By transforming sparse, fragmented accesses into a unified weight-stacked operation, we effectively saturated the High-Bandwidth Memory (HBM) of the NVIDIA A100.

These ratios (Equation 1) empirically validate the transition of the forward pass into a hardware-saturated, compute-bound state.

6.3 Numerical Parity and Model Integrity

To ensure that performance gains did not compromise model reasoning, we verified mathematical parity through the GSM8K benchmark. Both the baseline and FastLLaDAMoE yielded identical accuracy ($\approx 50\%$), confirming that our token reordering and binning operations are numerically sound. The minor response variance observed is statistically consistent with the stochastic nature of the diffusion process and does not represent a loss in model capability.

6.4 Implications for Alignment Research

The throughput enhancements provided by FastLLaDAMoE are instrumental for iterative alignment techniques such as Group Relative Policy Optimization (GRPO) Shao et al. [2024]. By reducing inference latency from approximately 90 seconds to under 50 seconds for complex reasoning tasks, our approach makes the RL-based training of diffusion language models computationally feasible on standard research hardware. This efficiency is a prerequisite for scaling alignment research to larger diffusion-based Mixture-of-Experts frameworks.

References

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A Additional Profiling Results

In this appendix, we provide detailed profiling traces of the FastLLaDAMoE implementation to substantiate the efficiency claims and analyze remaining bottlenecks.

A.1 Kernel Launch Overhead Analysis

While the token permutation mechanism successfully achieves contiguous memory access for expert computations, the current implementation relies on a Python-level loop for dispatching expert kernels.

Figure 5 illustrates a zoomed-in view of a single MoE layer execution. The colored blocks represent the batched General Matrix Multiplications (GEMMs) for sorted tokens. The gaps between these blocks (indicated by arrows) correspond to the CPU-bound overhead incurred by the Python interpreter and PyTorch dispatcher during kernel launches.

Figure 5: **Detailed Profiling of Kernel Launch Overhead.** The trace shows the execution of sorted expert kernels in FastLLaDAMoE. Although memory access is contiguous (indicated by solid colored blocks), the timeline reveals idle GPU intervals (black gaps) between consecutive expert calls. These gaps represent the latency introduced by the sequential Python dispatch loop, highlighting the potential for further acceleration via a fused Triton kernel.

A.2 Baseline vs. Optimized Execution

Figure 6 compares the fragmented memory access pattern of the baseline implementation against the sorted execution flow of our method.

Figure 6: **Execution Flow Comparison.** The trace demonstrates the effectiveness of the *Sort-Compute-Scatter* pipeline. The chaotic, fragmented kernel launches typical of standard MoE implementations are replaced by a structured sequence of batched operations, significantly improving GPU occupancy.